

THE IMPORTANCE OF MINDFULNESS PRACTICES IN SUPPORTING STUDENTS 'MENTAL HEALTH WITHIN FOREIGN LANGUAGE EDUCATION

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The 21st century is considered not only the era of up-to-date technologies and innovative approaches in the sphere of education, but also the time when there is a consistent need to maintain and support mental health. In the current ever-changing world, providing mental health support to students in the process of language teaching always stays on the agenda. Language acquisition, being a complex process, requires learners to be open-minded, stress-resilient, self-confident, and able to consistently motivate themselves to move forward. However, the vast majority of students find learning a new language as a challenging journey when there are always such struggles as shifts in motivation level, anxiety, the fear of mistakes, and peer pressure. Modern-day scientists and researchers suggest various ways of overcoming language learning related challenges, and one of the widely used practices is called mindfulness.

Mindfulness can be applied in different aspects of life, providing a positive impact on the mental health conditions of individuals. Babanoğlu and Atalmiş clearly define the notion by describing it as the practice that “concentrates on using consciousness and awareness in the present moment to control emotions and overcome challenges in life by boosting resilience, strengthening the force of resilience, and supporting general wellbeing” (2, p. 2). According to Albrecht (2015), in an academic environment, techniques of mindfulness enable to capture students attention as well as enhance their welfare (cited in 1, p. 897), which in turn creates a positive atmosphere for acquiring new knowledge effectively and avoiding burnout. This practice is even more needed when the subject being taught is a foreign language with its complicated grammatical structure, a huge amount of new vocabulary, and complex pronunciation which differs dramatically from students' native language, making it challenging to understand. What puts extra pressure on students is their fear of speaking in front of peers, as they can be judged for making errors. Therefore, correctly selected mindfulness methods are supposed to reduce language anxiety to a great extent. Furthermore, mindfulness practices enable students to concentrate on the subject and make it difficult to easily get bothered by varied distractions, which is quite handy in this very days as students' attention during class is shifting to gadgets.

Mindfulness interventions utilized in language teaching are various, and each of them has its of function for aiding students in language acquisition. The most

prominent among all techniques is meditation, which involves visualization, word repetition, and sound-based meditation. Apart from meditation practice, mindfulness includes breath-based, sensory awareness, and movement-based techniques.

The first, breath-related technique or mindful breathing, can be applied before starting a lesson. In this technique, students are asked to breathe by focusing on the moment they inhale and exhale. Such a simple, but strong technique decreases the level of rapid heartbeats as well as nervousness, thus providing a stress-free environment for learning. Practice is particularly handy if it is used as a pre-speaking exercise, facilitating learners' concentration and providing a “calm down effect”. The study conducted by Schmidt-Fajlik (3, p.8) in Japanese students whose target language was English revealed that mindful breathing exercises before extensive reading proved to be effective in reducing negative emotions and improving reading fluency.

The following method, which is also helpful in the language learning process, is sensory mindfulness. Sometimes students struggle with writing tasks during exam preparation or lose their concentration while reading a complex article in their target language during the class. In this very moment to release task-related stress or get some relaxation, students are suggested to utilize the “Five Step” exercise. The exercise requires the use of five senses, including seeing, hearing, feeling, smelling, and tasting. To do the exercise, all learners need to do is name five things they see, four things that they feel, three sounds they hear, two scents they smell, and a thing that they taste. Although diving into deep thoughts while doing this activity seems time-consuming, it provides quick relief from anxiety, which in turn brings positive academic outcomes.

Movement-based mindfulness interventions also have the potential to simplify language acquisition of learners, and a case in point is the technique called mindful walking. It involves walking back and forth in a quiet classroom for five or ten minutes. The technique can be utilized before organizing classroom discussions and debates, as it boosts mental clarity and helps students concentrate. Besides that, active walking from the medical perspective improves blood circulation inside the body, providing oxygen for better brain functionality.

All of the aforementioned techniques underscore the significance and benefits of mindfulness practices within the domain of foreign language teaching, demonstrating the fact that properly chosen techniques not only safeguard students' mental wellbeing during the lessons but also enhance their academic performance. The deliberate integration of such practices enables educators to nurture learners' emotional resilience. Further scholarly investigations and studies have the potential to widen the applicability of mindfulness-oriented practices across various educational contexts, creating stress-free environments within the classrooms.

Reference

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